

Development of Tractor Operated on Farm Pelleting Machine for Densified Fuel Production from Agro Residues

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ABSTRACT

India is a rapidly developing country experiencing significant economic and industrial growth leading to a substantial increase in energy demand. The primary energy sources meeting this demand are oil and coal. Among renewable energy options, bioenergy offers a viable pathway to address the rising energy needs through various biomass conversion technologies. Densification of loose agro-residues into pellets enhances ease of handling, storage, and transportation. At the village level, tractors are widely used by farmers as a primary power source for agricultural operations. In this context, a tractor-operated pelleting machine was developed to enable on-farm utilization of agro-residues for pellet production. Research experiments were designed using the Box–Behnken statistical model, varying moisture content, particle size, and feeding rate. The results indicated high pelleting efficiencies of 86.89% for soybean straw and 86.27% for cotton stalk, with corresponding calorific values of 4493.25 kcal/kg and 4632.18 kcal/kg, respectively. The tractor-operated pelleting machine, compatible with an 18-hp tractor, demonstrated effective performance under optimized conditions for soybean straw, with a pelleting efficiency of 86.89%, a pelleting capacity of 38.62 kg/h, a pellet density of 604.45 kg/m³, and a fuel consumption rate of 1.114 L/h. Soybean pellets exhibited superior durability (94.72%) compared to cotton pellets (92.36%), while energy density ratios were also favourable, at 4.22 for soybean and 4.01 for cotton. The tractor-operated pelleting machine, equipped with conveying and mixing arrangements, demonstrated effective performance at pilot scale, highlighting its potential for commercial adoption and sustainable biomass utilization at the village level.

Keywords: Biomass Pelletization; Cotton stalk; Soybean Straw; Pelleting Efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

The depletion of fossil resources and the persistent decline in environmental quality have intensified the global urgency to transition towards renewable energy alternatives. Biomass, being abundant, versatile, and cost-effective, has emerged as one of the most promising substitutes for fossil fuels due to its environmental benefits and diverse applications. Unlike fossil fuels,

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which are finite and associated with high greenhouse gas emissions, biomass is a renewable resource that can significantly reduce carbon emissions while meeting the energy demands of a growing global population. Biomass serves as an attractive feedstock owing to its renewability, abundance, and minimal environmental impacts, including negligible net carbon dioxide emissions and very low sulphur content (Tumuluru *et al.*, 2010).

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India, with its vast agricultural land area, generates substantial quantities of crop residues annually (Kumar *et al.*, 2015). These residues possess considerable potential as biomass feedstock for sustainable energy production (Yadav *et al.*, 2021). Globally, biomass currently contributes approximately 8-15% of the total energy supply in the form of electricity, heat, and transportation fuels. In several developing nations, its share reaches 40 -50%, primarily due to the local availability of biomass resources, which makes it a readily accessible energy option. Projections indicate that by 2050, biomass could meet 33 - 50% of the world's primary energy requirements, establishing it as a key component of the future global energy portfolio and an essential contributor to reducing dependence on non-renewable energy sources (Vassilev *et al.*, 2013). Given India's significant agricultural output and associated residue generation, the country holds immense potential to expand biomass-based energy solutions. Leveraging these resources could not only address energy security challenges but also promote environmental sustainability, rural development, and economic diversification through decentralized energy production.

The growing demand for renewable energy has driven a rapid expansion of the biomass pellet market, which increased from 2 MT in 2000 to 37 MT by 2015 - a remarkable 92% growth, as more countries recognize pellets' potential to meet energy needs (Jagtap and Kalbande, 2023). Low production costs, high energy content, and adaptability to both domestic and industrial uses make pellets an attractive renewable fuel option. Projections indicate that continued technological improvements, infrastructure development, and research investment will further accelerate the growth of the global pellet industry (Liu *et al.*, 2014).

This study presents a significant improvement over conventional pelleting machines, such as piston, screw, and hydraulic presses, which are constrained by dependence on electricity, immobility, and manual feeding - limitations

particularly relevant in rural India, where electricity supply is unreliable. The innovation lies in the development of a tractor-operated pelleting machine integrating power transmission with automated feeding and mixing systems. Designed for off-grid applications, the system eliminates the need for grid electricity, reduces labour intensity, lowers operational costs, and enhances worker safety. Field testing with cotton stalks and soybean straw demonstrated the machine's ability to optimize the pelleting process, offering a practical, sustainable, and economically viable approach for decentralized biomass utilization.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Selection of Feedstock

Cotton stalks and soybean straw were selected as the agro-residues for pellet production in this study. Prior to pelleting, the materials underwent shredding to achieve the desired particle size, as size reduction is a crucial pre-processing step that enhances pellet quality and densification efficiency. The feedstocks were sourced from the fields of the Central Research Station and the Cotton Research Centre of Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth (PDKV), Akola. The shredded residues were then used directly in the pelleting experiments.

2.2. Design Consideration

The pelleting machine and its components were designed based on the following parameters. The target machine capacity (Q) was set at 50 kg/h, with the bulk density (ρ) of the feedstock material ranging between 150–200 kg/m³ (Kankuka and Osu, 2013; Chikwado, 2013). For efficient operation, the die shaft speed was maintained in the range of 150-250 rpm (Kai *et al.*, 2010). The die diameter was selected as 200 mm, while the roller diameter was 120 mm. To ensure mobility and suitability for rural applications, the machine was designed to be powered by a small tractor with an engine capacity of 18-28 hp.

2.3. Development of Tractor Operated Biomass Pelleting Machine

A power transmission system utilizing a small tractor was previously developed for operating the pelletizing machine. In the present design, to improve operational efficiency and reduce drudgery, the system was integrated with automated feeding and mixing mechanisms. The power transmission assembly for biomass mixing, feeding, and pelletizing.

The power transmission from the tractor PTO to the main shaft was achieved using a mini tractor (VST Mitsubishi Shakti – model 180D). The PTO operated at a speed of 540 ± 10 rpm, with the tractor engine rated at 18 hp. The actual power available at the PTO was 13 hp. Power from the

main shaft was transmitted to a gearbox attached to the pelletizing unit, which operated at a 7:1 ratio, thereby increasing the shaft speed to 1600 rpm as required for the pelletizing process. Simultaneously, the PTO speed was transmitted from the main shaft to counter shaft A via a belt and pulley system. Counter shaft A was connected to counter shaft B through an additional belt and pulley system, reducing the rotational speed to 270 rpm. From counter shaft B, power was transmitted to the mixer shaft, achieving a mixer shaft speed of 81 rpm. Counter shaft B also drove counter shaft C, where the speed was further reduced to 135 rpm using the same belt and pulley arrangement. Finally, counter shaft C powered the conveyor shaft, which operated at the required speed of 81 rpm.

Fig. 1. A view of the tractor operated pelletizing machine

This integrated system allowed the tractor to power the pelletizing, feeding, and mixing units simultaneously, enhancing process efficiency, reducing manual labour, and ensuring uniform feedstock preparation before pelletizing. The construction and operation of the tractor-operated pelletizing machine are shown in Fig. 1.

The torque values for different shafts in the tractor-operated pelletizing machine were determined based on the tractor's PTO power output and corresponding shaft speeds (Ramteke and Sirohi, 2003). The torque transmitted by the main shaft was calculated as 171.58 Nm and remained the same for counter shaft A, as both pulleys had equal diameters. With speed reductions at subsequent shafts, the torque increased accordingly:

counter shaft B (343.17 Nm at 270 rpm), mixer shaft (1143.90 Nm at 81 rpm), counter shaft C (686.34 Nm at 135 rpm), and the inclined elevator shaft, which operated at the same speed as the mixer shaft (1143.90 Nm). These values illustrate the effect of speed reduction on torque multiplication within the machine's transmission system, ensuring adequate power transmission to the feeding, mixing, and pelleting units.

2.4. Pellet Production Process

The pellet production process involved three main stages: raw material pre-treatment, pelletization, and post-treatment. During experiment, a tractor-powered pelleting machine was developed, provided with an inclined belt conveyor and a mixer. Soybean straw and cotton stalk residues were first ground using a hammer mill equipped with 4 mm, 6 mm, and 8 mm sieves, resulting in size-classified samples for uniform pellet production. The shredded biomass was then loaded into the hopper of the inclined belt conveyor, which transported the material to the mixer. The material was mixed with water at moisture content levels of 20%, 25%, and 30%, using a tractor operated mixer provided with blades attached to a horizontal shaft.

After thorough mixing, the material was discharged into the pelleting machine at controlled feeding rates of 45, 50, and 55 kg/h. In pelleting chamber, two rollers pressed the feedstock into die holes, forming uniform pellets as friction increased the temperature of the die plate and rollers, as well as the pellets, to 70–72°C. External heating or binding agents were not used during the entire process. Pellets with a diameter of 15 mm and a length of 40 mm were produced using the tractor-operated pelleting machine. After pelletization, the pellets were sun-dried and stored in airtight bags to prevent moisture absorption.

2.5. Performance Evaluation of the Tractor Operated Pelleting Machine

2.5.1. Experimental design

The effect of key parameters such as moisture content, particle size, and feeding rate were studied to evaluate the performance of the tractor-operated pelleting machine with reference to pelleting efficiency, pellet density, fuel consumption and pelleting capacity (Jagtap and Kalbande, 2023). The experiments were planned using a Box-Behnken randomized design at the levels of the independent variables indicated in Table 1. The process parameters, moisture content, particle size, and feeding rate were optimized using Design-Expert software (version 13.0.5.0) and the effects and interactions of these variables were analyzed.

2.5.2. Determination of pelleting efficiency

The ratio of the total mass of pellets produced to the total mass of biomass feedstock, expressed in percentage is known the pelleting efficiency and estimated as given below:

$$\eta_p = \frac{W_p}{W_t} \times 100 \quad \dots (1)$$

Where, η_p is the pelleting efficiency, %; W_p is total mass of pellets produced by the machine, kg and W_t is the total mass of input, kg.

2.5.3. Determination of pelleting capacity

The pelleting capacity is calculated (eq. 2) as the ratio of the total quantity of the feed pelleted to the time taken (Okewole and Lgbeka 2016).

$$C_p = \frac{W_p}{T} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where, C_p is the pelleting capacity (kg/h) and T is the time taken to pelletize the specified feed, h

Table 1. The variables associated with the evaluation of the pelleting machine and the pellets.

Independent variables				
Sl. No.	Variables	Levels (coded and decoded)		
		1	0	-1
1.	Moisture content, %	20	25	35
2.	Particle size, mm	4	6	8
3.	Speed of shaft, rpm	150	200	250
Dependent variables				
Performance of pelleting machine		Qualities of pellets		
1.	Pelleting efficiency	1. Moisture Content	2. Pellet durability	
2.	Pelleting capacity	3. Volatile matter	4. Calorific value	
3.	Pellet density	5. Ash content	6. Volumetric	energy
4.	Fuel consumption	7. Fixed carbon	density ratio	

2.5.4. Bulk density of pellets

This is the mass per unit volume of the bulk material including the pore volume. Determined as the ratio of the mass (kg) occupying a given bulk volume to the volume of the container (m³).

2.5.5. Fuel consumption

The fuel consumption by the tractor during pellet production was determined by filling method, where the fuel tank was initially filled with diesel up to the full level and the quantity to top up to the same level is the fuel consumed (Shahid *et al.*, 2019). This was followed for each test run.

2.6. Physiochemical Properties of Biomass Pellets

The physical and thermal properties were evaluated using the most optimal pellet combination. It includes proximate analysis, calorific value, shattered index, resistance to water penetration, pellet durability and energy density ratio were studied.

2.6.1. Proximate analysis

The proximate composition such as moisture, volatile matter, ash content and fixed carbon

content of the biomass were carried out following the standard procedures (Bhavsar *et al.*, 2018).

2.6.1.1. Moisture content

The moisture content of biomass was measured by the oven dry method. Initially the sample with the known weight was kept in a thermostatically controlled ventilated hot air oven maintained at $105 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ until the constant weight is attained (ASTM D-3173). Then the oven dry sample was weighed and the moisture content was estimated as percentage on dry basis.

2.6.1.2. Volatile matter

The volatile matter was determined as per the procedure of ASTM, D-3175 by heating the sample in a silica crucible at $950^\circ\text{C} \pm 25^\circ\text{C}$ in a muffle furnace for 7 minutes.

2.6.1.3. Ash content

The amount of ash collected by heating a moisture-free sample in a muffle furnace without a lid at a temperature of 750°C for 30 min. as per ASTM D – 3174, was expressed as a percentage based on the quantity of the sample taken.

2.6.1.4. Fixed carbon

The fixed carbon content is the value obtained by subtracting the values of moisture content, volatile matter, and ash content from one hundred percent.

2.6.2. Calorific value

Calorific value is the amount of heat generated by unit mass of the fuel on its complete combustion. The calorific value of biomass was determined by using bomb calorimeter. The calorific value of biomass using bomb calorimeter was determined by following formula.

$$C = \frac{(W+w) \times (T_2 - T_1)}{X} \quad \dots (3)$$

Where, C is the calorific value, kcal/kg; W is the weight of water in calorimeter, kg; w is the water equivalent of apparatus, kcal/°C; T_1 is the initial temperature of water, °C; T_2 is the final temperature of water, °C and X is the weight of sample, g.

2.6.3. Shattered index

The shattered index test evaluates the hardness of the briquettes. A pellet of known weight and length was dropped from a height of one meter onto a concrete floor ten times. The weight and size of the disintegrated pellet were recorded, and the percentage of material loss was calculated. The shatter resistance of the pellet was then determined using the following formula. (Madhava *et al.*, 2012).

$$\text{Percentage weight loss, } L = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100 \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{Tumbling resistance} = 100 - \text{\% weight loss} \quad \dots (5)$$

Where, W_1 and W_2 are the weight of the pellet before and after tumbling, g, respectively.

2.6.4. Resistance to water penetration

The percentage of water absorbed by the pellets was measured by immersing each pellet in 25 mm of water at 27°C for 30 seconds. The percent

water gain was calculated and recorded using the following formula (Sengar *et al.*, 2012):

$$G = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100 \% \quad \dots (6)$$

$$R = 100 - G \quad \dots (7)$$

Where, G is the water gained by the pellets, %; R is the resistance to water penetration, %; W_1 and W_2 are the weight of the pellet before and after immersion in water, g, respectively.

2.6.5. Pellet durability

Pellet durability refers to the ability of pellets to withstand destructive loads and frictional forces during handling and transport. According to ASABE (ASAE S269.4 DEC1991, R2007), the durability of the pellets was assessed by placing 500 g of pellets in a tumbling box device. The pellets were tumbled for 10 minutes at a speed of 50 rpm. After tumbling, the broken and cracked pellets were separated, and their weight was recorded. The durability was then calculated using the following formula.

$$D = \frac{W_a}{W_b} \times 100 \quad \dots (8)$$

Where; D is the pellet durability, %; w_a is the mass of the pellet after shaker treatment, g and w_b is the mass of the pellet before shaker treatment, g.

2.6.6. Energy density ratio

The energy density ratio is the ratio of energy content per unit volume of raw material to the energy content per unit volume of pellet fuel. The energy density ratio of pellet fuel is calculated by using the equation as below (Sengar *et al.*, 2012):

$$ED = \frac{\rho_p \times CV_{Pellet}}{\rho_A \times V_{Agro\ residue}} \quad \dots (9)$$

Where, ED is the energy density ratio; ρ_p is the pellet density, kg/m³; ρ_A is the bulk density of agro residue, kg/m³; CV_{pellet} is the higher heating value of pellet, kcal/kg and $CV_{Agro\ residue}$ is the higher heating value of agro residue, kcal/kg.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Physicochemical Properties of Biomass

Prior to conducting the experiments, the physical and chemical properties of soybean straw and cotton stalks, *viz.*, bulk density, calorific value, moisture content, volatile matter, ash content and fixed carbon were determined and presented in Table 2.

The bulk densities of soybean straw and cotton stalk were measured as 175.85 kg/m³ and 182.65 kg/m³, respectively. Calorific values of 3863.42 kcal/kg for soybean straw and 3726.38 kcal/kg for cotton stalk, confirming their potential as viable bioenergy feedstocks. From the proximate analysis the soybean straw contained 10.61% moisture, 70.64% volatile matter, 3.88% ash, and 14.87% fixed carbon. In comparison, cotton stalk contained 10.19% moisture, 72.84% volatile matter, 4.28% ash, and 12.69% fixed carbon. These parameters are essential for understanding the thermal behaviour and densification performance of biomass during pelletization.

The comprehensive characterization of soybean straw and cotton stalk demonstrates their favourable physicochemical properties, making them suitable candidates for conversion into biomass pellets or other biofuels. Their utilization can contribute to renewable energy production in the agricultural sector while supporting sustainable waste management practices.

3.2. Performance Evaluation of Tractor Operated Pelleting Machine

3.2.1. Pelleting efficiency

As moisture content increased from 25% to 35%, and the feeding rate decreased from 55 kg/h to 45 kg/h, a notable increase in the pelleting efficiency was observed for both soybean and cotton stalks, as seen from in Fig. 2a and 2b. The highest pelleting efficiency of 87.79% for soybean straw and 86.12% for cotton stalk, was achieved at a moisture content of 35%, particle size of 6 mm, and feeding rate of 45 kg/h. On the contrary, the lowest efficiency, 80.54% for soybean straws and 79.03% for cotton stalks, was observed at a moisture content of 25%, with the same particle size (6 mm) and a higher feeding rate of 55 kg/h.

The results demonstrated that optimizing moisture content and feeding rate plays a critical role in enhancing the pelleting process. Higher moisture levels, coupled with lower feeding rates, promote improved particle binding, leading to more efficient pellet formation and increased pellet durability. These findings suggest the necessity of precise optimization of parameters to maximize the operational efficiency of tractor-operated pelleting machines, particularly for agricultural biomass such as soybean and cotton stalks.

Table 2. Physicochemical properties of biomass

Parameter	Biomass	
	Soybean straw	Cotton stalk
Bulk density, kg/m ³	175.85	182.65
Calorific value, kcal / kg	3726.38	3863.4
Moisture content, % d.b.	10.61	10.19
Volatile matter, %	70.64	72.84
Ash content, %	3.88	4.28
Fixed carbon, %	14.87	12.69

a. Soybean straw

b. Cotton stalk

Fig. 2. Effect of moisture content and feeding rate on pelleting efficiency

a. Soybean straw

b. Cotton stalk

Fig.3. Effect of moisture content and feeding rate on pelleting capacity

3.2.2. Pelleting capacity

As the moisture content increased from 25% to 35%, significant increase in pelleting capacity was observed (Fig. 3a and 3b). The increase in moisture content enhanced the plasticity and cohesiveness of the raw materials leading to better pellet formation during the densification process. At a moisture content of 35%, maximum pelleting capacities of 48.83 kg/h for soybean straws and 48.76 kg/h for cotton stalks were recorded when combined with a feeding

rate of 55 kg/h and a particle size of 6 mm. This suggests that higher moisture levels, in conjunction with optimal feeding rates, create favourable conditions for continuous and efficient pellet production. The minimum pelleting capacities of 33.87 kg/h and 33.42 kg/h for soybean and cotton stalks, respectively, were observed at a reduced feeding rate of 45 kg/h, a lower moisture content of 25%, and a particle size of 6 mm.

The reduction in pelleting capacity at lower moisture content may be attributed to insufficient binding of particles, resulting in less cohesive pellets. Thus maintaining a balance between moisture content and feeding rate is critical to achieve higher pelleting capacity and efficiency.

3.2.3. Pellet density

The study revealed a clear trend in pellet density with varying moisture content for soybean and cotton stalks. As the moisture content decreased from 35% to 25%, there was a significant increase in pellet density, as illustrated in Fig. 4a and 4b. Lower moisture content tends to reduce the amount of water within the biomass, allowing for a more compact arrangement of particles during the pelleting process, which results in denser pellets. The maximum pellet density of 616.25 kg/m³ for soybean straws and 612.96 kg/m³ for cotton stalks were achieved at a moisture content of 25%, with a particle size of 4 mm and a feeding rate of 50 kg/h. In contrast, the minimum pellet densities of 598.65 kg/m³ and 595.98 kg/m³ for soybean and cotton stalks, respectively, were observed at a higher moisture content of 35%, a larger particle size of 8 mm, and the same feeding rate of 50 kg/h. These findings indicate that lower moisture content promotes greater compaction of biomass particles, leading to higher pellet densities. On the other hand, higher moisture content reduces the mechanical pressure required for densification, resulting in less compact pellets.

3.2.4. Fuel consumption

The study revealed a direct relationship between feeding rate and the tractor's fuel consumption during the pelleting process. The highest fuel consumption was recorded at 1.178 L/h for soybean straw and 1.171 L/h for cotton stalk, observed at a feeding rate of 55 kg/h, with a particle size of 8 mm and a

moisture content of 30% (Fig. 5a and 5b). This increase in fuel usage at higher feeding rates is likely due to the greater load on the pelleting machine, requiring more effort from the tractor to process the material, which in turn raised energy demand. In contrast, the lowest fuel consumption was measured at 1.112 L/h for soybean straw and 1.103 L/h for cotton stalk, corresponding to a feeding rate of 45 kg/h, a particle size of 4 mm, and a moisture content of 30%. Smaller particle sizes facilitate smoother handling and compaction, thereby reducing the mechanical resistance in the pelleting chamber and minimizing fuel requirements.

3.3. Physiochemical Properties of Biomass Pellets

3.3.1 Proximate analysis

The moisture content of soybean and cotton stalk pellets was found to be 3.45% and 4.11%, respectively, which are ideal levels for storage and transport (Table 3). Moisture levels below 10% are preferred, as they enhance the stability and durability of the pellets, while higher moisture content reduces the available heat for combustion, negatively affecting energy efficiency.

The volatile matter content of the pellets was found to be 73.79% for soybean straws and 74.39% for cotton stalks, indicating high reactivity and ease of ignition. These values suggest that both types of pellets would combust readily, making them suitable for use as fuel. Additionally, the ash content was found to be at 5.23% for soybean pellets and 5.56% for cotton pellets, which is within acceptable limits for biomass fuel and affects the handling of combustion residues. The fixed carbon content was 17.43% for soybean pellets and 15.94% for cotton pellets, providing an estimate of their heating value and contribution to long-term combustion (Table 3)

a. Soybean straw

b. Cotton stalk

Fig. 4. Effect of moisture content and feeding rate on pellet density

a. Soybean straw

b. Cotton stalk

Fig. 5. Effect of particle size and feeding rate on fuel consumption

Table 3. Proximate analysis of soybean and cotton pellets

Biomass	Moisture content, %	Volatile matter, %	Ash content, %	Fixed carbon, %	Calorific value, kcal/kg
Soybean pellets	3.45	73.89	5.23	17.43	4493.25
Cotton pellets	4.11	74.39	5.56	15.94	4632.18

3.3.2. Calorific value

The calorific value is a crucial property of biomass fuel, as it is influenced by both the chemical composition of the material and its moisture content. The calorific values for soybean and cotton pellets were found to be 4493.25 kcal/kg and 4632.18 kcal/kg, respectively (Table 3). These values indicate that cotton pellets possess a higher energy content compared to soybean pellets, which can have important implications for their use as a fuel source. Higher calorific values suggest better efficiency and performance during combustion, making cotton pellets a more advantageous option for energy production.

3.3.3. Shattered index

The shattered index is a critical property used to assess the strength of pellets against shattering. The shattered index was found to be 91.89% for soybean pellets and 90.68% for cotton pellets. These values indicate that both types of pellets exhibit a high level of structural integrity, making them suitable for transportation. A higher shattered index signifies that the pellets are less likely to break or crumble under stress, which is vital for minimizing losses and maintaining fuel quality.

3.3.4. Resistance to water penetration

The water penetration resistance of soybean and cotton pellets was measured, resulting in values of 84.92% and 83.46%, respectively. These high resistance values indicate that both types of pellets have a strong ability to withstand moisture, which is crucial for maintaining their integrity during storage and transportation. Effective water resistance helps prevent the degradation of pellets, ensuring that their physical and chemical properties remain intact, thereby enhancing their overall performance as biomass fuel.

3.3.5. Pellet durability

The pellet durability test was conducted for both soybean and cotton pellets and resulting in an average material loss of less than 7% to 8% during the tumbling test. The durability percentages were

94.72% for soybean pellets and 92.36% for cotton pellets. These high durability values suggest that both types of pellets exhibit excellent structural integrity, making them suitable for commercial applications. The ability to maintain durability under mechanical stress is crucial for reducing material losses and ensuring the consistent quality of biomass fuel pellets throughout their life cycle.

3.3.6. Energy density ratio

The energy density ratios for soybean and cotton pellets were measured and found to be 4.22 and 4.01, respectively. These results demonstrate that the volumetric energy density of the pellets is significantly higher than that of the original biomass material, with an increase of 4.22 times for soybean pellets and 4.01 times for cotton pellets. This substantial enhancement in energy density reveals that both types of pellets can provide a more concentrated energy source, making them more efficient for use as biofuel.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The tractor-operated pelleting machine, compatible with an 18-hp tractor, demonstrated effective performance under optimized conditions for soybean straw, achieving a pelleting efficiency of 86.89%, a pelleting capacity of 38.62 kg/h, a pellet density of 604.45 kg/m³, and a fuel consumption rate of 1.114 L/h. Cotton stalk exhibited a higher bulk density (182.65 kg/m³) and calorific value (3863.42 kcal/kg) compared to soybean straw, and pelletization further increased the calorific value to 4493.25 kcal/kg for soybean and 4632.18 kcal/kg for cotton. Soybean pellets exhibited superior durability (94.72%) compared to cotton pellets (92.36%), while energy density ratios were also favourable, at 4.22 for soybean and 4.01 for cotton. Economic evaluation confirmed the viability of the machine, with a net present worth of ₹4,737,488 over a 10-year period, a benefit–cost ratio of 2.15, a short payback period of 6.13 months, and an internal rate of return of 46%.

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